

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Material identification (clone- rootstock combinations)

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

DELIVERABLE D2.1

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework - NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Phenotyping is essential in biological and agronomical research for characterizing phenotypic traits in living organisms. The University of Torino's new plant phenotyping platform, PhenoPlant, offers a non-invasive, high-throughput tool that integrates advanced technologies for precise and comprehensive plant analysis. Utilizing PhenoPlant, a study on drought responses in grafted grapevines revealed significant differences in performance based on rootstock/scion combinations, underscoring the importance of selecting appropriate pairings for optimal drought tolerance.

Note: images are not included in this deliverable at this time, as they have not been published in a scientific journal yet (a paper is in preparation).

Plant Phenotyping Setup

Plant Material and Growth Conditions

The study was conducted at the Department of Food and Agricultural Sciences (DISAFA) in Grugliasco, Torino, Italy, involving 11 combinations of grapevine cuttings. These combinations included two clones of *Vitis vinifera* (Pinot Noir 20VCR and Nebbiolo 430VCR) grafted onto both drought-tolerant and drought-sensitive rootstocks. The grafted vines were initially grown in polytunnels and later transferred to the PhenoPlant platform, a controlled environment facility where climate conditions were meticulously monitored.

Experimental Design

The grapevines were divided into two groups: drought stress and irrigation, and placed on the PhenoPlant Platform scales using Latin square randomization. The irrigated plants were automatically watered to maintain pot capacity throughout the experiment, while the drought treatment received irrigation only at the experiment's start (Figure 1). During the stress phase, sensors automatically recorded and uploaded environmental data (light, temperature, humidity, and CO₂) as well as pot weight and irrigation data every 10 minutes to the platform's software.

Table 1: Grapevine clone and rootstocks combination with relative rootstock drought sensitivity and number of plants per combination.

Grapevine cultivar	Clone	Rootstocks	Rootstocks drought sensitivity	Number of replicas
Pinot Noir	VCR 20	Kober 5 BB	Low	12
Pinot Noir	VCR 20	1103 Paulsen	High	12
Pinot Noir	VCR 20	SO4	Low	12
Pinot Noir	VCR 20	M2	High	12
Pinot Noir	VCR 20	140Ru	High	12
Nebbiolo	VCR 430	Kober 5 BB	Low	12
Nebbiolo	VCR 430	1103 Paulsen	High	12
Nebbiolo	VCR 430	SO4	Low	12
Nebbiolo	VCR 430	420 A	Low	12
Nebbiolo	VCR 430	110R	High	12
Nebbiolo	CVT 185	Gravesac	Medium	12

Figure 1: a) Pictures of the phenotyping platform Phenoplant, equipped with Phenospex® (Heerlen, The Netherlands) PlantEye F400™ and Droughtspotter™ scales. b) Experimental scheme.

Phenotyping and Physiological Measurements

Plant responses were monitored using non-destructive phenotyping and physiological tools, as well as a destructive method. The Phenospex® PlanEye F500 sensor, mounted on a gantry inside the PhenoPlant Platform (Figure 1), was used for morphological and spectral analysis. The CIRAS-4 portable gas-exchange fluorescence system (PPSystem, USA) measured leaf stomatal conductance (gs), assimilation (A), transpiration (E), and stomatal CO₂ concentration (C_i). Stem water potential (Ψ_{stem}) was measured using a Scholander pressure chamber (Soilmoisture Equipment Corp., Santa Barbara, CA).

Morphological and Spectral Analysis

The PlanEye F500 sensor measures absorbance from visible light (red: 620-645 nm; green: 530-540 nm; blue: 460-485 nm) to near-infrared (NIR: 720-750 nm) and collects plants' spatial coordinates to calculate morphological parameters and create 3D plant representations. Morphological parameters such as plant height, leaf area, and surface angle, and spectral parameters like Green Leaf Index (GLI) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) are calculated using HortControl 3.0 software (Phenospex). This spectral sensor is mounted on a gantry that moves at 25 mm s⁻¹, and to scan the entire platform it takes approximately 2.5 hours. The measurements were conducted twice daily from 6:00 to 8:30 AM and PM to better understand the drought impact on plants through spectral indexes.

Physiological Analysis

Three types of measurements were performed: gas exchange, evapotranspiration (Droughtspotter), and stem water potential (Ψ_{stem}).

Gas Exchange Measurements - The CIRAS-4 system monitored drought stress responses by measuring leaf A and gs under light saturation conditions, ensuring a photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) greater than 400 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Measurements were taken daily from 8:30 to 10:00 AM (right after the spectral sensor finished scanning the plants) on one leaf per plant, with CO₂ concentration in the cuvette set to 400 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{air}$.

Stem Water Potential (Ψ_{stem}) - Ψ_{stem} measurement is reliable for irrigation management, and it is performed by using a Scholander pressure chamber. For this experiment, three replicates per treatment were used to assess plant water status and determine drought stress levels.

Evapotranspiration - Droughtspotter - Automated scales recorded pot weight every 10 minutes, providing insights into water loss and irrigation status. To eliminate water evaporation, pots were covered or an identical soil-filled pot at field capacity was placed on another scale. The near-continuous data collection enabled detailed studies of evapotranspiration on daily and hourly scales.

Statistical Analysis

Preliminary analysis of the dataset was conducted using HortControl software. Due to the extensive data, the dataset was compartmentalized into distinct files. Basic charts were produced using Excel to highlight significant differences. The dataset was normalized to achieve a normal distribution, and key time points were isolated. Heatmaps, graphs, and correlation charts were generated using SRplot, an online platform for data visualization and graphing.

Analysis of Rootstock/Scion Combinations

All data, including spectrometric and physiological measurements, were analyzed across all rootstock/scion combinations under both well-watered and drought conditions. A strong correlation was observed for many of these measurements. This guided a comprehensive analysis of the drought responses in eleven grapevine/rootstock combinations using the PlantEye and Drought Spotter profiles, focusing particularly on Surface Leaf Angle Average, Green Leaf Index, and weight. The data revealed significant differences in these indices among the various combinations under both well-watered and drought conditions. Notably, the variability in response between stressed and non-stressed plants underscored the complexity of drought stress physiology, which is further complicated by the interaction between scion and rootstock. A clear distinction is observed between known drought-tolerant rootstocks (1103P, 110R, 140Ru, and M2) and less drought-tolerant rootstocks (Kober 5BB, SO4, 420A, and Gravesac) across all measured indices. This pattern is consistent in both Nebbiolo and Pinot Noir scions, suggesting that the rootstock plays a crucial role in the grapevine's drought response, irrespective of the scion variety. The observed differences in drought tolerance among the rootstock/scion combinations are critical for improving grapevine management and breeding programs. Spectrometric indices were more effective in distinguishing between tolerant and sensitive rootstocks during severe stress. The 1103P rootstock was easily identifiable as more drought-tolerant, while Kober 5BB was identified as less tolerant. The Drought Spotter also reached the same conclusion, albeit with less pronounced differences.

Physiological Analysis: Rootstocks Drought Tolerance Comparison: K5BB vs. 1103P

Using the CIRAS-4 system, the results indicate that all four combinations (scion/rootstocks) exhibit variable but stable $A/E/G_s$ values in non-stressed conditions across all measurement times. Under stress, there is a notable reduction in all those parameters, particularly at T2-S and, in certain combinations, demonstrate a significant response to water stress through reduced stomatal opening and increased transpiration with higher photosynthesis rate. This variability across different rootstocks and varieties suggests varying levels of drought tolerance or

sensitivity, which is crucial for understanding plant responses to drought and managing irrigation in viticulture.

Stomatal Conductance (Gs) - The datasets summarise stomatal conductance (Gs) measurements for Nebbiolo and Pinot grapevine varieties, grafted onto 1103 Paulsen (1103P) or Kober 5BB (K5BB) rootstocks, under stressed and non-stressed conditions, using the CIRAS-4 system. Higher stomatal conductance was observed in non-stressed plants, with a pronounced reduction under stress, particularly at T2-S, indicating a strong response to water stress through reduced stomatal opening. This variability in response across different rootstocks and varieties suggests differing levels of drought tolerance or sensitivity.

Transpiration (E) - Analysing the transpiration rates (E) undergoing drought stress for Nebbiolo and Pinot varieties grafted onto 1103 Paulsen and Kober 5BB rootstocks reveals insights into their drought tolerance. Nebbiolo grafted onto 1103 Paulsen exhibited the highest transpiration rate under stress, marking it as the most tolerant combination to drought conditions. This higher transpiration rate suggests that Nebbiolo on 1103 Paulsen maintains better physiological activity under stress.

Photosynthesis Rates (A) - Examining the net photosynthesis rates (A) with water removal for the Nebbiolo and Pinot varieties grafted onto 1103 Paulsen and Kober 5BB rootstocks provide valuable insights into their photosynthetic efficiency during drought conditions. Nebbiolo grafted onto 1103 Paulsen demonstrated the highest photosynthesis rate under drought stress, indicating it as the most tolerant combination to drought in terms of maintaining photosynthetic activity.

Water Potential (Ψ) - Analysing the water potential (Ψ) and weight (W) across different scion/rootstock combinations provides insights into their physiological responses under varying conditions. The Nebbiolo grafted onto 1103 Paulsen combination shows a notable ability to maintain a relatively stable water potential and recover weight effectively, suggesting it might be more resilient under variable conditions. This combination exhibited the highest recovery in weight and maintained moderate fluctuations in water potential, indicating effective physiological management under stress.

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